

Reactions of Tertiary Bases with bis Propylenediamine Nickel (II) Chloride

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Nickel bis propylenediamine on being treated with alkali or pyridine, β -or γ -picoline results in the formation of tris-propylenediamine nickel chloride and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ or $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})_4\text{Cl}_2]$ (L = pyridine, β -or γ -picoline), respectively. The reaction has been explained to be due to the disproportionation of the octahedral intermediates. α -picoline with $-\text{CH}_3$ at α -position can bring about the reaction only when it is used in large excess. The compounds have been characterised by analysis, magnetic and visible spectral studies.

It has been observed that on treatment with alkali mono-ethylenediamine copper complex gets converted into bis-ethylenediamine form. Under similar conditions bis-ethylenediamine nickel complex is converted into tris form. It is said to be due to the intermediate formation of hydroxo complex and its ultimate disproportionation¹. In the reaction of bis-ethylenediamine nickel complex and tertiary bases, similar disproportionation of unstable mixed ligand intermediates (of bis-ethylenediamine nickel and tertiary bases), is seen to form tris-ethylenediamine nickel(II) and tetra pyridine nickel(II)². In the present investigation reactions of alkali and tertiary bases on bis-propylenediamine nickel chloride have been studied.

Nickel chloride used was of BDH (A.R.) quality and the organic ligands were of Fluka pure quality. Bis-propylenediamine nickel chloride was prepared by the method suggested for the ethylenediamine analogues³ and was analysed.

To a concentrated solution of bis-propylenediamine nickel chloride was added 1M solution of sodium hydroxide. The blue solution turned pink and some hydroxide got precipitated. The filtrate was concentrated to get pink crystals. It was recrystallised and analysed.

To other parts of concentrated bis-propylenediamine nickel chloride were added 5 ml. of 1M solution of pyridine, β - and γ -picolines separately. The solutions turned bluish pink. They were concentrated to get mixed blue and pink crystals. The blue crystals were dissolved in ethanol and recrystallised. The pink crystals remained undissolved. Both the compounds were dried and analysed. Even on the addition of small quantities of the tertiary base, pink colour appears in $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ solution. The reaction was repeated with α -picoline. No change was observed on addition of small quantity of α -picoline to $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2]\text{Cl}_2$. However, on adding excess of α -picoline, the solution turned 'pink with the precipitation of $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. The solution was filtered and concentrated, only pink crystals were obtained.

The magnetic moments of the solids were determined by Gouy method and the absorption spectra of the solids in chloroform were obtained by Spectromom Spectrophotometer in the range 400–1000 nm. The results have been tabulated below.

TABLE

Analytical data and other properties of the complexes

Substance	Calc. %			Found %			B.M.
	Ni	Cl	N	Ni	Cl	N	
[Ni(pn) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (light violet)	18.17	22.59	8.92	18.61	22.52	8.81	—
[Ni(pn) ₃]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (pink)	15.13	18.28	10.82	15.17	18.30	10.75	2.81
[Ni(py) ₄]Cl ₂ (blue)	13.16	15.90	12.56	13.10	15.80	12.42	3.16
[Ni(β -pic) ₄]Cl ₂ (blue)	11.69	14.12	11.15	11.60	14.10	11.03	3.09
[Ni(γ -pic) ₄]Cl ₂ (blue)	11.69	14.12	11.15	11.55	14.07	10.95	3.12

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formation constant values in solution indicate that pyridine and substituted derivatives³ are weaker ligands than propylenediamine⁴ and hence ligand exchange is unlikely. The reaction can be explained by considering that [Ni(pn)₂]Cl₂ combines with two -OH^- groups or base molecules to form intermediate [Ni(pn)₂(OH)₂] or [Ni(pn)₂L₂]Cl₂ respectively. These unstable octahedral intermediates undergo disproportionation resulting in [Ni(pn)₃]Cl₂ and Ni(OH)₂ or [Ni(pn)₃]Cl₂ and [Ni(L)₄]Cl₂, respectively. Pyridine β - and γ -picoline bring about the disproportionation reaction but under same conditions α -picoline does not react, because with a -CH_3 group at α -position it is sterically hindered from forming the octahedral intermediate and this in turn prevents disproportionation. On adding excess of α -picoline, however, the pH increases and reaction similar to that in case of sodium hydroxide can thus be expected, resulting in the products [Ni(pn)₃]Cl₂ and Ni(OH)₂. There will, therefore, be no formation of [Ni(α -pic)₄]Cl₂. The reactions can be represented as follows :

where L = pyridine, β - or γ -picoline.

The above is however only a probable mechanism. The magnetic moment. (~ 2.8 B.M.)⁵ and the absorption spectra of the pink compound in all cases correspond to spin-free octahedral structure as expected for [Ni(pn)₃]Cl₂.⁶

In cases of blue complexes [Ni(L)₄]Cl₂ the magnetic moments correspond to spin only value of two electrons. This indicates distorted octahedral structure with chloride ions in the coordination. [Ni(L)₄]Cl₂ is soluble in chloroform, and their solutions are non-conducting. The nature of the absorption spectra in chloroform correspond to distorted

octahedral structure. The intensity of the peaks are low ($\epsilon = \sim 12.0$) corresponding to the octahedral structure. These seem to confirm that the chloride ions are present in the coordination sphere.

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REFERENCES

1. J. Wagner-Janregg, B. E. Hackley Jr., T. A. Lies, O. O. Owens and R. Proper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 929.
2. D. C. Patel, R. C. Sharma and P. K. Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 927.
3. *Inorganic Synthesis*, Vol. VI, McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc., New York, 1960, p. 198.
4. A. E. Martell and Malvin Calvin, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds, Prentice Hall, 1956, p. 522.
5. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advance Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1962, p. 738.
6. R. S. Drago, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1968, p. 179.

